

TIME-DEPENDENCY PHENOMENA IN BIAXIALLY ORIENTED POLYPROPYLENE and SELF REINFORCED POLYPROPYLENE LAMINATES

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ORIENTED POLYMERS

Uniaxial orientation

- ⊕ High properties along **ONE** direction
- ⊖ **Large** property **GAPS** between the stretched and not stretched directions

SRPP tapes

Biaxial orientation

- ⊕ Good properties along **TWO** directions
- ⊕ **Limited** property **GAPS** between the two directions

BOPP films

ORIENTED POLYMERS

BOPP films

SRPP fabrics

Excellent interfaces

ORIENTED POLYMERS

BOPP films

SRPP fabrics

Excellent interfaces

Recyclability

ORIENTED POLYMERS

BOPP films

SRPP fabrics

Excellent interfaces

Recyclability

High toughness

ORIENTED POLYMERS

BOPP films

SRPP fabrics

Excellent interfaces

Recyclability

High toughness

Low cost

ORIENTED POLYMERS

BOPP films

SRPP fabrics

Excellent interfaces

Recyclability

High toughness

Low cost

Formability

ORIENTED POLYMERS

BOPP films

SRPP fabrics

Excellent interfaces

Recyclability

High toughness

Low cost

Formability

Different textural look

ORIENTED POLYMERS

BOPP films

ORIENTED POLYMERS

BOPP films

ORIENTED POLYMERS

BOPP films

SRPP fabrics

ORIENTED POLYMERS

BOPP films

SRPP fabrics

TIME-DEPENDENCY ANALYSIS

TIME ?

TIME

TIME ?

TIME

EXPERIMENTAL PART

MANUFACTURING

BOPP film laminate

MANUFACTURING

BOPP film laminate

MANUFACTURING

BOPP film laminate

SRPP woven laminate

MANUFACTURING

BOPP film laminate

SRPP woven laminate

MANUFACTURING

BOPP film laminate

SRPP woven laminate

MANUFACTURING

BOPP film laminate

SRPP woven laminate

TESTING

BOPP film laminate

SRPP woven laminate

TESTING

BOPP film laminate

SRPP woven laminate

TESTING

BOPP film laminate

SRPP woven laminate

Three-point bending test results

BOPP

Three-point bending test results

SRPP

Three-point bending test results

Gaps between timeslots statistically analyzed

BOPP

MD: 34% in 1 months

TD: 32% in 1 months

Stabilization after 1 month

MD = Machine Direction; TD = Transverse Direction

Three-point bending test results

Gaps between timeslots statistically analyzed

BOPP

MD: 34% in 1 months

TD: 32% in 1 months

Stabilization after 1 month

SRPP

MD: +24% in 1 month

TD: +16% in 1 month

Stabilization after 1 month

MD = Machine Direction; TD = Transverse Direction

DSC analysis

BOPP Variation < 10%

SRPP Variation < 20%

CONCLUSIONS

BOPP

Flexural properties are **TIME-DEPENDENT**

Crystallinity degree is **NOT AFFECTED** by time

SRPP

Flexural properties are **TIME-DEPENDENT**

Crystallinity degree is **MORE AFFECTED** by time

Ideal testing time:
AT LEAST AFTER ONE MONTH

Ideal testing time:
AT LEAST AFTER ONE MONTH

Future work

BOPP

SRPP

Study on the internal stresses and its contribution

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